

A framework for analog-digital mixed-precision neural network training and inference

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Abstract—Recent advancements in AI hardware highlight the potential of mixed-signal accelerators, which integrate analog computation for matrix multiplications with reduced-precision digital operations, to achieve superior performance and energy efficiency. In this paper, we present a framework designed to perform hardware-aware training and inference evaluation of neural networks (NNs) on such accelerators. This framework extends an existing toolkit, the IBM Analog Hardware Acceleration Kit (AIHWKit) [1], using a quantization library, enabling flexible layer-wise deployment in either analog or digital units, the latter with configurable precision and quantization options. Our combined framework supports simultaneous quantization- and analog-aware training as well as post-training calibration routines. It can also evaluate the accuracy of NNs when deployed on mixed-signal accelerators. We demonstrate the need of such a tool through ablation studies on a ResNet-based vision model and a BERT-based language model, highlighting the importance of its functionality for maximizing accuracy during deployment. Our contribution will be open-sourced as part of the core code of AIHWKit in an upcoming release.

Index Terms—Analog in-memory computing, Mixed-precision computing, neural network training

I. INTRODUCTION

INNOVATION in AI has led to the widespread adoption of neural networks (NNs) across various scientific fields and everyday applications. Due to their increasingly ubiquitous presence, significant research efforts are focused on the development of efficient hardware to deploy these models. Conventional AI accelerators, based on the von Neumann architecture, face challenges due to the large amount of data that need to be shuttled between the memory and the processing elements, a fundamental bottleneck for NN workloads [2], [3]. Naturally, in-memory computing (IMC) has emerged as a promising alternative, providing a solution to the von Neumann bottleneck. One specific type of IMC, analog in-memory computing (AIMC), leverages the physical characteristics of resistive memory devices to perform matrix-vector multiplications (MVMs) directly within the memory array. AIMC has garnered significant attention from many research groups, with numerous promising demonstrations with various memory technologies in the literature [4]–[7].

AIMC NN accelerators are designed to capitalize on the incredible performance attainable when performing MVM operations using AIMC, which are both the most prominent and computationally expensive operations in NN workloads. However, contemporary NN architectures comprise of more than just MVMs; they also require operations like normal-

Fig. 1. High-level depiction of an analog-digital mixed-precision NN accelerator comprised of AIMC tiles and reduced precision DPUs. The input and output of the AIMC tiles are quantized to the width of the communication fabric, while the DPUs also operate in reduced precision internally.

ization, pooling, various non-linear functions, and especially in transformers, dynamic MVMs [8], [9]. As these operations cannot effectively be executed in the analog domain, current research is focused on designing analog-digital mixed-precision systems [10]. For these accelerators, most MVMs are executed in the analog domain to leverage its high efficiency and parallelism, while the rest of the operations are executed in digital processing units (DPUs), with data communication usually handled by a digital communication fabric. Fig. 1 gives an overview of these systems and how operations are mapped to the different units.

One key challenge in architecting heterogeneous systems like these is integrating digital components that can sustain the processing rate of the AIMC tiles, while maintaining a respectable level of energy-efficiency. As such, most architectures utilize low-precision DPUs for digital compute

and use reduced activation width, the latter to minimize the communication fabric footprint. However, these decisions introduce a new aspect to one of analog computing’s primary issues: precision. It is well substantiated in the literature that the effective deployment of NNs in AIMC hardware requires the networks to be trained in an analog hardware-aware (HWA) manner [11], [12]. During this process, NNs are exposed to analog non-idealities during training, increasing their robustness to noise when deployed on hardware [5]. Furthermore, it is well documented that aggressive quantization of NNs can result in accuracy degradation, which can only be recovered through quantization-aware training (QAT) or with sophisticated post-training quantization (PTQ) algorithms [13]. Therefore, we believe that for effective deployment of NNs on analog-digital mixed-precision accelerators, a combined analog- and quantization-aware training procedure is essential to be studied.

Despite the widespread agreement of this hardware approach by the community, there is still no unified tool capable of handling both types of training for a given NN. Additionally, no single tool exists to handle post-training simulations that study the effects of these phenomena, forcing researchers to rely on a patchwork of different libraries to conduct their studies. This paper addresses this gap by introducing a PyTorch-based unified framework that enables training, post-training calibration, and inference simulations for NN deployment on analog-digital mixed-precision hardware. Our framework extends the capabilities of a sophisticated analog HWA training and inference simulation framework, the IBM Analog Hardware Acceleration Kit (AIHWKit) [14], by integrating in its source code a flexible quantization library [15] and building a cohesive infrastructure to map a given NN to a heterogeneous accelerator, with layer-wise customization options for deployment targets (analog or digital of varying precision) and parameters (activation width, quantization method, etc.). In the following section, we introduce the capabilities of the unified framework and the infrastructure that enables flexible mapping of a NN to heterogeneous units, highlighting its customizability and ease of use. We then showcase the tool’s capabilities by presenting various ablation studies conducted using a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a Transformer network, before concluding the paper.

II. QUANTIZATION LIBRARY AND INTEGRATION WITHIN THE AIHWKIT

A. Quantization library and functionality

There are many libraries which can be used to perform QAT and PTQ on NNs. Most are proprietary, but some are open-source, like Brevitas [16] and the Quantization API of PyTorch. For our integration, we want to utilize a framework that provides easy integration with PyTorch and, ideally, be lightweight, adding minimal overhead to the training time without sacrificing in functionality. After experimentation with various open source libraries, we found that the library used in [15] to study Transformer quantization provides high-performance with many options and is entirely written in

PyTorch. Additionally, it is extendable to custom modules, providing a safeguard for future architectures. The library, as presented in [15] supports the following: **A** Definition of arbitrary layers whose activations, weights, or both, are quantized in integer precision of configurable size (IntX). Additionally, custom modules can be defined in which quantization happens in the internal activation flow, e.g., between the key-query multiplication and the softmax in the multi-head attention module; **B** A series of estimators to optimally calibrate the quantization range for each activation or weight tensor when doing PTQ or when training with straight-through estimation; **C** Treating the quantization scales as a trainable parameter, letting the backwards pass find optimal quantization parameters.

B. AIHWKit

Several AIMC simulation frameworks exist that are geared towards performing HWA training and inference simulation [14], [17], [18]. From these frameworks, AIHWKit [14] is amongst the most popular ones because of its configurability and seamless integration with PyTorch.

At a conceptual level, when a NN is consumed by the AIHWKit, it will search for and replace all layers which can be decomposed to MVMs – e.g., Linear and Conv2D layers – with an analog counterpart, using the `convert_to_analog` function. These analog layers map the weights of the layer to virtual analog tiles, which are code constructs that simulate a hardware AIMC tile. For example, during training, it can introduce noise to the weights in the forward pass, to simulate the noise of the resistive devices as well as quantization on the output of the tile to simulate the analog-to-digital conversion effect of the hardware. For more detail about its capabilities, we refer the reader to [19].

C. Unified framework

We elected to integrate AIHWKit and [15] within the AIHWKit codebase to avoid excessive fragmentation by introducing another open-source repository. For this integration, we incorporated the library code from [15] into AIHWKit with minimal structural adjustments, while preserving its original functionality.

Inspired by the simplicity of calling `convert_to_analog`, we created a counterpart function, called `convert_to_quantized`, to quantize any PyTorch model with configurable options. This function also iterates over the layers of the network and converts them to quantized counterparts, if such a conversion is defined. To achieve this, the user defines quantized modules to serve as the counterpart of conventional PyTorch modules (e.g., `QuantBatchNorm2d` instead of `BatchNorm2d`), and then selects the quantization parameters of the quantized modules, like the precision, the quantization method, range estimators and other parameters for weights and/or activations using our infrastructure.

To map a given NN in an arbitrary analog-digital manner, the user can use a two-step approach, combining the `convert_to_analog` and `convert_to_quantized`

Fig. 2. Two-step conversion process from a floating-point NN to analog-digital mixed-precision NN with configurable parameters (weight and activation precision, asymmetric quantization, granularity) using our framework. Parameters are configurable on a per-layer basis.

functions. This approach is applied visually on a CNN model in Fig. 2. First, the user can convert the floating point network from PyTorch to a network with analog layers. This conversion step follows the standard AIHWKit flow, which can be found in [19]. In this step, the user can define the resistive-processing unit configuration (RPUConfig) for the virtual tiles, which includes options for training and inference. Additionally, the user can select to exclude some layers from this conversion, in case these layers are to remain in floating point or mapped to low-precision digital units in the next step. In this step, all layers that do not contain weights remain in floating point. This step is shown in Fig. 2 as Step 1 in the code section.

Next, the user needs to select the quantization options for the layers that are to be quantized. Specifically, the user defines the correspondance between PyTorch modules and quantized modules for the conversions and then provides an instance of the `LayerQuantizationConfig` dataclass that contains the quantization parameters for the quantized module. These parameters can be selected separately for the activations and the weights. They include the number of bits, whether the quantization is symmetric or asymmetric, and other options (see [15]). These options can be defined either at a module level (quantize all modules of the same type the same way) or at the instance level (quantize an indicated instance of a module with the selected way). All these options are then placed in the `QuantizationMap` dataclass which is passed to the `convert_to_quantized` function that performs the conversion. This step is shown in Fig. 2 as Step 2.

In the example shown in Fig. 2, we first convert the

model to analog, excluding the first and last layers of the network, a common practice to boost CNN performance on AIMC [20]. Then, we configure the quantization, by defining the conversion from PyTorch modules to quantized modules (see `module_specific_layer_qconfig`) and the quantization parameters for each conversion (see `layer_qconfig_8bits` and `layer_qconfig_4bits`). Note that only module-specific conversions are demonstrated here. Finally, the conversion finishes with the `convert_to_quantized` call, to get the final mixed-precision network.

In addition to quantizing PyTorch modules, we augment the tiles defined in AIHWKit with quantized periphery functionality. Specifically, the AIHWKit tiles contain code to rescale the outputs of the virtual crossbar with affine factors, stemming from the mapping of weights to resistances, drift compensation, etc. These operations are usually executed at the periphery of AIMC tiles, in reduced precision [21]. As such, we integrate code to quantize the column-wise affine scales and the bias of the tiles, bringing AIHWKit simulation closer to reality. Additionally, we introduce a new tile, called `QuantizedTorchInferenceTile`, whose final output is again quantized down to a configurable size, independent of the precision of the analog-to-digital converters, as it is the case in modern AIMC designs [5].

Finally, after a model is converted by replacing all modules with analog or quantized counterparts, one can proceed to training or inference using the conventional AIHWKit and PyTorch infrastructure, without needing any changes to ex-

TABLE I
QUANTIZATION ABLATION USING RESNET32 FOR CIFAR-10.

Weights Mapped	Activation Precision	PTQ	QAT
Baseline		94.12%	
Analog	FP	93.83 \pm 0.21%	
	Int8 [†]	92.41 \pm 0.25%	93.87 \pm 0.17%
	Int8 [◇]	92.43 \pm 0.25%	93.76 \pm 0.28%
	Int6 [†]	91.58 \pm 0.15%	93.04 \pm 0.18%
	Int6 [◇]	91.24 \pm 0.31%	93.18 \pm 0.17%
Mixed	Int8 [†]	93.09 \pm 0.18%	93.93 \pm 0.08%
	Int8 [◇]	93.14 \pm 0.20%	94.00 \pm 0.15%
	Int6 [†]	91.76 \pm 0.35%	93.10 \pm 0.17%
	Int6 [◇]	91.98 \pm 0.33%	93.06 \pm 0.20%

[†] Symmetric quantization. [◇] Asymmetric quantization.

* Mixed weight mapping indicates that the first convolutional layer and the last linear layer are mapped in digital, using Int8 precision for the weights.

isting code. To be able to evaluate a quantized model without retraining, post-training calibration routines to configure the quantization parameters of all quantized layers are provided.

III. DEMONSTRATIONS

We demonstrate the capabilities of our framework by presenting two ablation studies, on a vision and a language model. We study the accuracy impact when mapping these models on a heterogeneous accelerator with analog and digital units of configurable precision and a communication fabric of configurable width. For the studies below, all inputs to the AIHWKit tiles have Int8 precision when the activations of other layers have the same or higher precision. If an activation width lower than Int8 is specified, the activation width is used as the precision of inputs to the AIHWKit tiles.

First, we investigate a ResNet32 model trained on the CIFAR-10 dataset. Initially, we test how the network performs when we change the activation width from floating point down to 6 bits. We present the accuracy results on the upper part of Table I, when performing either PTQ or QAT using our tool. To perform the PTQ studies, we start with the network that was analog-aware retrained, but with floating point activations, quantize its activations and perform a calibration step using data from the training set (25 batches of 128 images). We observe that PTQ reduces the accuracy of the network by $> 1\%$ when Int8 is adopted and that asymmetric quantization does not help recovering performance. When QAT is performed simultaneously with the analog-aware retraining, accuracy is recovered, with $< 1\%$ drop even when going down to Int6 activations.

Next, we demonstrate another capability of the tool, by deploying the weight layers of the network in a mixed manner. Specifically, we deploy the first and last layers of the network in a digital unit, that operates with the weights in Int8 precision, quantizing the weights symmetrically per-channel. The selection to deploy these specific layers on digital comes from observation that these are the most sensitive, as they act as the feature extractor and the classifier respectively [20].

TABLE II
QUANTIZATION ABLATION USING BERT FOR SQUADV1.1.

Weights Mapped	Activation Precision	PTQ	QAT
Baseline		88.21%	
Analog	FP	87.27 \pm 0.10%	
	Int12 [†]	87.35 \pm 0.10%	87.27 \pm 0.11%
	Int12 [◇]	87.35 \pm 0.13%	87.27 \pm 0.07%
	Int10 [†]	87.18 \pm 0.05%	87.18 \pm 0.10%
	Int10 [◇]	87.24 \pm 0.13%	87.20 \pm 0.07%
	Int8 [†]	85.43 \pm 0.17%	85.71 \pm 0.18%
	Int8 [◇]	86.89 \pm 0.10%	86.69 \pm 0.15%

[†] Symmetric quantization. [◇] Asymmetric quantization.

After mapping the weight layers of the network in the mixed manner, we perform the same activation-width study as before. We observe similar tendencies when it comes to PTQ and QAT but with overall higher accuracies compared to the deployment of all weights on analog. Note that PTQ is also applied on the weights of the first and last layers of the network which are now deployed in digital.

Our second demonstration investigates the deployment of BERT trained on SQuADv1.1 in a mixed-precision accelerator. This network is significantly more sensitive to activation quantization, as studied in [15]. We study its deployment with all the weights on analog and sweeping the activation width from floating point down to 8 bits. The results show that activation-width below 10-bit yields a drop of $> 1\%$ from the baseline. For Int8 activations, adopting asymmetric quantization enhances accuracy by $\sim 1\%$, but still shows a drop of $> 1\%$ compared to the baseline. Finally, for this network, we see that PTQ and QAT yield similar results.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented a unified framework to perform training and inference simulations for analog-digital mixed-precision NN accelerators. We extended the AIHWKit, a powerful toolkit for AIMC simulation, with a quantization library, and built a flexible infrastructure to map an arbitrary NN to either analog or digital units, additionally configuring the width of the activations. Our tool was used to perform sensitivity studies on a ResNet32 and on a BERT model deployed on mixed-precision systems. The libraries we built upon provide further capabilities that are not demonstrated here, like treating the quantization parameters as trainable parameters and more advanced range estimators for PTQ. The framework, along with the code to replicate the results presented here, will be open sourced as part of the AIHWKit.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Rasch, T. Gokmen, D. Moreda, M. Le Gallo, and K. El Maghraoui, "IBM Analog Hardware Acceleration Kit," <https://github.com/IBM/aihwkit>, 2024, v. 0.9.2.
- [2] A. Reuther, P. Michaleas, M. Jones, V. Gadepally, S. Samsi, and J. Kepner, "Ai and ml accelerator survey and trends," in *2022 IEEE High Performance Extreme Computing Conference (HPEC)*, 2022. doi: 10.1109/HPEC55821.2022.9926331 pp. 1–10.
- [3] A. Sebastian, M. Le Gallo, R. Khaddam-Aljameh, and E. Eleftheriou, "Memory devices and applications for in-memory computing," *Nature Nanotechnology*, vol. 15, no. 7, pp. 529–544, Jul 2020. doi: 10.1038/s41565-020-0655-z
- [4] W. Wan, R. Kubendran, C. Schaefer, S. B. Eryilmaz, W. Zhang, D. Wu, S. Deiss, P. Raina, H. Qian, B. Gao, S. Joshi, H. Wu, H.-S. P. Wong, and G. Cauwenberghs, "A compute-in-memory chip based on resistive random-access memory," *Nature*, vol. 608, no. 7923, pp. 504–512, Aug 2022. doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04992-8
- [5] M. Le Gallo, R. Khaddam-Aljameh, M. Stanisavljevic, A. Vasilopoulos, B. Kersting, M. Dazzi, G. Karunarathne, M. Brändli, A. Singh, S. M. Müller, J. Büchel, X. Timoneda, V. Joshi, M. J. Rasch, U. Egger, A. Garofalo, A. Petropoulos, T. Antonakopoulos, K. Brew, S. Choi, I. Ok, T. Philip, V. Chan, C. Silvestre, I. Ahsan, N. Saulnier, V. Narayanan, P. A. Francese, E. Eleftheriou, and A. Sebastian, "A 64-core mixed-signal in-memory compute chip based on phase-change memory for deep neural network inference," *Nature Electronics*, Aug 2023. doi: 10.1038/s41928-023-01010-1
- [6] T.-H. Wen, J.-M. Hung, W.-H. Huang, C.-J. Jhang, Y.-C. Lo, H.-H. Hsu, Z.-E. Ke, Y.-C. Chen, Y.-H. Chin, C.-I. Su, W.-S. Khwa, C.-C. Lo, R.-S. Liu, C.-C. Hsieh, K.-T. Tang, M.-S. Ho, C.-C. Chou, Y.-D. Chih, T.-Y. J. Chang, and M.-F. Chang, "Fusion of memristor and digital compute-in-memory processing for energy-efficient edge computing," *Science*, vol. 384, no. 6693, pp. 325–332, 2024. doi: 10.1126/science.adf5538. [Online]. Available: <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.adf5538>
- [7] L. Fick, S. Skrzyniarz, M. Parikh, M. B. Henry, and D. Fick, "Analog matrix processor for edge ai real-time video analytics," in *2022 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference (ISSCC)*, vol. 65, 2022. doi: 10.1109/ISSCC42614.2022.9731773 pp. 260–262.
- [8] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep residual learning for image recognition," in *2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, Jun 2016. doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2016.90 pp. 770–778.
- [9] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, L. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin, "Attention is all you need," in *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, ser. NIPS'17. Red Hook, NY, USA: Curran Associates Inc., 2017. ISBN 9781510860964 p. 6000–6010.
- [10] S. Jain, H. Tsai, C.-T. Chen, R. Muralidhar, I. Boybat, M. M. Frank, S. Woźniak, M. Stanisavljevic, P. Adusumilli, P. Narayanan, K. Hosokawa, M. Ishii, A. Kumar, V. Narayanan, and G. W. Burr, "A heterogeneous and programmable compute-in-memory accelerator architecture for analog-ai using dense 2-d mesh," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 114–127, 2023. doi: 10.1109/TVLSI.2022.3221390
- [11] M. J. Rasch, C. Mackin, M. Le Gallo, A. Chen, A. Fasoli, F. Odermatt, N. Li, S. R. Nandakumar, P. Narayanan, H. Tsai, G. W. Burr, A. Sebastian, and V. Narayanan, "Hardware-aware training for large-scale and diverse deep learning inference workloads using in-memory computing-based accelerators," *Nature Communications*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 5282, Aug 2023. doi: 10.1038/s41467-023-40770-4
- [12] G. W. Burr, H. Tsai, W. Simon, I. Boybat, S. Ambrogio, C.-E. Ho, Z.-W. Liou, M. Rasch, J. Büchel, P. Narayanan, T. Gordon, S. Jain, T. M. Levin, K. Hosokawa, M. Le Gallo, H. Smith, M. Ishii, Y. Kohda, A. Chen, C. Mackin, A. Fasoli, K. ElMaghraoui, R. Muralidhar, A. Okazaki, C. T. Chen, M. M. Frank, C. Lammie, A. Vasilopoulos, A. M. Friz, J. Luquin, S. Teehan, I. Ahsan, A. Sebastian, and V. Narayanan, "Design of analog-ai hardware accelerators for transformer-based language models (invited)," in *2023 International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM)*, 2023. doi: 10.1109/IEDM45741.2023.10413767 pp. 1–4.
- [13] A. Gholami, S. Kim, Z. Dong, Z. Yao, M. W. Mahoney, and K. Keutzer, "A survey of quantization methods for efficient neural network inference," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.13630>
- [14] M. J. Rasch, D. Moreda, T. Gokmen, M. Le Gallo, F. Carta, C. Goldberg, K. El Maghraoui, A. Sebastian, and V. Narayanan, "A flexible and fast pytorch toolkit for simulating training and inference on analog crossbar arrays," in *2021 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Circuits and Systems (AICAS)*, 2021. doi: 10.1109/AICAS51828.2021.9458494 pp. 1–4.
- [15] Y. Bondarenko, M. Nagel, and T. Blankevoort, "Understanding and overcoming the challenges of efficient transformer quantization," in *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, M.-F. Moens, X. Huang, L. Specia, and S. W.-t. Yih, Eds. Online and Punta Cana, Dominican Republic: Association for Computational Linguistics, Nov. 2021. doi: 10.18653/v1/2021.emnlp-main.627 pp. 7947–7969. [Online]. Available: <https://aclanthology.org/2021.emnlp-main.627>
- [16] A. Pappalardo, "Xilinx/brevitas," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3333552>. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3333552
- [17] X. Peng, S. Huang, H. Jiang, A. Lu, and S. Yu, "Dnn+neurosim v2.0: An end-to-end benchmarking framework for compute-in-memory accelerators for on-chip training," *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, vol. 40, no. 11, pp. 2306–2319, 2021. doi: 10.1109/TCAD.2020.3043731
- [18] C. Lammie and M. R. Azghadi, "Memtorch: A simulation framework for deep memristive cross-bar architectures," in *2020 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, 2020. doi: 10.1109/ISCAS45731.2020.9180810 pp. 1–5.
- [19] M. Le Gallo, C. Lammie, J. Büchel, F. Carta, O. Fagbohunge, C. Mackin, H. Tsai, V. Narayanan, A. Sebastian, K. El Maghraoui, and M. J. Rasch, "Using the IBM analog in-memory hardware acceleration kit for neural network training and inference," *APL Machine Learning*, vol. 1, no. 4, p. 041102, 11 2023. doi: 10.1063/5.0168089. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0168089>
- [20] K. Ueyoshi, I. A. Papiastas, P. Houshmand, G. M. Sarda, V. Jain, M. Shi, Q. Zheng, S. Giraldo, P. Vranx, J. Doevenspeck, D. Bhattacharjee, S. Cosemans, A. Mallik, P. Debacker, D. Verkest, and M. Verhelst, "Diana: An end-to-end energy-efficient digital and analog hybrid neural network soc," in *2022 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference (ISSCC)*, vol. 65, 2022. doi: 10.1109/ISSCC42614.2022.9731716 pp. 1–3.
- [21] E. Ferro, A. Vasilopoulos, C. Lammie, M. L. Gallo, L. Benini, I. Boybat, and A. Sebastian, "A precision-optimized fixed-point near-memory digital processing unit for analog in-memory computing," in *2024 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, 2024. doi: 10.1109/ISCAS58744.2024.10558286 pp. 1–5.